

Adapting Interaction Control in Robot-Aided Rehabilitation Using Reinforcement Learning

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Abstract—Adapting control strategy parameters in robot-aided rehabilitation is an important task to enhance the patients’ engagement and recovery. Thus, this work investigated the feasibility of applying a Reinforcement Learning algorithm to automatize the learning process. A Q-learning algorithm dynamically adjusts the interaction stiffness taking as input the motor performance and physiological state of the user. The experiments demonstrated the feasibility of the proposed approach and the ϵ -greedy capability in learning an optimal policy.

Index Terms—Upper-limb robot-aided rehabilitation, Reinforcement Learning, Q-Learning, Human-Robot Interaction

I. INTRODUCTION

Robot-aided rehabilitation offers a targeted approach with intense, highly repetitive, and functional movements for people suffering from neurological and musculoskeletal disorders [1]. Adapting control strategy parameters, such as stiffness, allows for the customization of the robot assistance level to match each patient’s specific pathology and progress, thereby enhancing their active engagement and accelerating recovery of impaired motor functions. However, manual tuning of control parameters, while effective, is complex and highly dependent on the therapist’s expertise, which can lead to reduced repeatability and reliability [2].

Supervised learning methods have enabled the development of interaction controllers that automatically adjust assistance levels based on Human-Robot Interaction (HRI) force data, but they require prior knowledge of task kinematics and dynamics [3]. In contrast, Reinforcement Learning (RL) can model HRI dynamics without detailed task information, using trajectory errors or interaction forces [4]. However, while RL can estimate control parameters based on patient models, the patient performance was never taken into account [5].

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This work aimed to explore the feasibility of dynamically adapting interaction control parameters based on the individual’s real-time state. Specifically, the goal was to develop a personalized policy for each user to enhance their performance during robot-aided rehabilitation sessions. An RL-based adaptation strategy was proposed to adjust the assistance level, i.e. the stiffness control parameter, according to the physiological condition and motor performance of the user. Additionally, two exploration strategies, ϵ -greedy and Upper Confidence Bound (UCB), were analyzed to determine which method is more effective in optimizing the RL-based adaptation system.

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

The block scheme of the proposed reinforcement learning-based interaction control adaptation strategy is shown in Fig. 1. Specifically, the block diagram includes the *Adaptive Interaction Controller*, the *Multimodal Monitoring* system, and the *Reinforcement Learning-based Adaptation* strategy.

Fig. 1. Proposed reinforcement learning-based interaction control adaptation strategy.

The *Adaptive Interaction Controller* adjusts the interaction dynamics between the robot and the user (further information

about the adaptive interaction control strategy can be found in [1]). It calculates the joint torques τ_c based on the difference between the desired trajectory and the user's actual position along the radial and tangential direction of motion. The control law includes a variable radial stiffness matrix (K_r) that the proposed RL-based approach can modify.

During the human-robot interaction session, the user is equipped with a *Multimodal Monitoring* system that allows the collection of physiological responses and kinematic performance of the user. The acquisition of Heart Rate (*HR*) and Respiration Rate (*RR*) offers insights into physical exertion [6]. Motor performance is quantified employing the Aiming Angle (θ_{aim}). It assesses the capability to perform a motion aiming toward the desired target.

Lastly, the *Reinforcement Learning-based Adaptation* strategy dynamically adjusts the radial stiffness K_r based on the user's physiological state and motor performance. More in detail, a Q-learning system is employed to learn the optimal adaptation policy by evaluating six possible states, defined by the current stiffness and the user's physiological condition, which can either be normal (*N*) or altered (*A*), according to the *HR* and *RR* values. Actions (increase, decrease, or maintain constant K_r) are taken every three point-to-point movements, rewarding actions according to the subsequent user performance θ_{aim} .

To guide the learning process, various exploration strategies can be used to balance exploration and exploitation. In this paper, ϵ -greedy and UCB were tested for their effectiveness in addressing this trade-off [7]. The ϵ -greedy strategy introduces randomness to promote exploration, while UCB selects actions based on $a_t = \arg \max(Q(s_t, a) + \text{bonus}(s_t, a))$, where bonus reflects how often an action has been chosen in state s_t , encouraging exploration of less frequently selected actions.

A. Experimental Evaluation

To determine which exploration strategy, between ϵ -greedy and UCB, is more effective in the proposed RL-based adaptation system, some experiments were carried out enrolling 10 healthy participants. The KUKA Light Weight Robot (LWR) 4+ runs the aforementioned *Adaptive Interaction Control* and provides data to compute the kinematic performance at 100 Hz. The possible radial stiffness values are $\{100, 500, 1000\}$ N/m. The BioHarness Chest Belt, developed by ZephyrTM Technology, is employed to acquire *HR* and *RR* at 1 Hz. Additionally, participants were guided through a virtual reality interface that displayed their assigned trajectory and current position. The Q-table update equation (see Fig. 1) implements a learning rate $\alpha = 0.1$ and discount factor $\gamma = 0.9$.

The enrolled participants were randomly divided into two experimental groups of 5 subjects each, G_1 (24.40 ± 3.58 mean age) and G_2 (26.40 ± 3.58 mean age), testing the ϵ -greedy and UCB exploration strategies, respectively. Each participant was asked to perform 81 three-dimensional point-to-point movements with the robot aid.

The modification of the reward (ΔR), calculated as the difference between the last and the first rewards obtained

during the experiment, has been calculated for both G_1 and G_2 . Moreover, the *Exploration Ratio (ER)* indicator, defined as the ratio between the number of explored actions and the number of possible actions, was computed to evaluate the exploration capability for *N* and *A* states. The Mann-Whitney statistical test was applied to identify differences between the collected performance indicators. The significance level was set at p -value = 0.05.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The ϵ -greedy strategy achieved a mean increase in the reward $\Delta R = 0.17 \pm 0.05$, while the UCB strategy showed a negative change in performance, with a mean $\Delta R = -0.07 \pm 0.04$. Statistical comparison revealed that ϵ -greedy was the more effective approach for this application, as indicated by a p -value < 0.01 . The *ER* of G_1 achieved 0.87 ± 0.14 for *N* and 0.38 ± 0.28 for *A*. Differently, the *ER* of G_2 was 0.82 ± 0.09 for *N* and 0.30 ± 0.24 for *A*. Due to the nature of the analyzed sample population, higher *ER* values were obtained for the *N* condition. Moreover, a statistically significant difference was found between ϵ -greedy and UCB in the *N* condition (p -value = 0.04).

These results suggest that ϵ -greedy provided a better balance between exploration and exploitation, allowing the participant to interact with an adaptive system that allow them to obtain their best θ_{aim} .

IV. CONCLUSIONS

This work provided a preliminary evaluation of the feasibility of applying a *RL* approach to robot-aided rehabilitation, using θ_{aim} as the reward measure. Two different exploration strategies were tested and compared revealing the ϵ -greedy as the best-performing one. Future work will focus on gathering additional data and incorporating other control parameters that can be adjusted to further enhance the system adaptability.

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